

The effect of the streaming instability on protoplanetary disc dust emission

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According to the core accretion theory, rocky planets form in protoplanetary discs by growing the initial μ -sized dust grains up to the size of a planet. This growth process can be divided into three main stages: grain growth (from $\sim \mu\text{m}$ to $\sim \text{cm}$), planetesimal formation (from $\sim \text{cm}$ to $\sim \text{km}$) and protoplanet formation (from $\sim \text{km}$ to $\sim 10^3 - 10^4 \text{ km}$). The planetesimal formation stage is particularly problematic due to the so-called "radial drift barrier", which hinders the formation of km-sized objects. The aerodynamical interaction between the dust and the gas, in fact, causes the dust grains to lose angular momentum and drift inwards; the efficiency of this interaction is measured through the Stokes number τ_s , a dimensionless quantity related to the grain size and disc parameters: the closer is τ_s to 1, the stronger is the interaction, and thus the radial drift. For typical disc parameters, $\tau_s \sim 1$ corresponds to grain sizes of $\sim \text{cm}$, which are thus expected to rapidly drift inwards, becoming unavailable to form planetesimals.

A potential solution to this problem is the streaming instability, an hydrodynamical instability that promotes the formation of dust overdensity regions, which can help the planetesimal formation in a twofold way: on one hand, the overdense regions interact differently with the gas, determining a reduction in the radial drift velocity; on the other hand, they can become dense enough to promote rapid gravitational collapse and planetesimal formation. The efficiency of streaming instability depends on the local system's properties: the grain Stokes number τ_s , proportional to the grain size (favourable condition: $\tau_s \sim 1$); the pressure support Π (which influences the dust-gas interaction); and the local dust to gas mass ratio Z (which must be high enough to trigger the instability).

In this context, our goal is to check if observational data contain signatures of streaming instability by comparing the emission properties in the mm of simulated systems undergoing streaming instability to recent data in the Lupus star forming region [2, 3]. Since the dust clumps formed via streaming instability are too small to be directly observed, we probe them through observable quantities; in particular, we consider the optically thick fraction, defined as the ration between the system's flux and the flux that it would emit if it were a black body,

$$ff = \frac{F_{\nu,\text{system}}}{F_{\nu,\text{bb}}}; \quad (1)$$

and the spectral index

$$\alpha = \frac{\partial \log F_{\nu,\text{system}}}{\partial \log \nu}, \quad (2)$$

and compare the simulations' distribution to the data distribution in the $ff - \alpha$ plane, studied by [2, 3].

Dust clump formation

We perform 12, 2D, local simulations of systems including 28 particle species (characterised by different Stokes numbers) with the hybrid hydrodynamical code ATHENA. Following previous studies of the parameter space [e.g. 4], we choose combinations of parameters (Stokes numbers, dust to gas mass ratio and particle mass distribution) that are expected to trigger streaming instability. After evolving each simulation until the formed clumps have reached a steady state, we compute the dust density profile for each particle species before (see the left panel in Figure 1) and after (right panel) particle clumping, noticing that the biggest particles in the simulations – i.e. those with τ_s close to 1 – participate in clumps (e.g., the magenta and blue lines in the Figure), whereas the smaller ones tend to remain uniformly distributed in the background (e.g., orange, yellow and green lines).

Figure 1: Particle density distribution before (left panel) and after (right panel) clump formation. The different colours refer to different Stokes numbers (see the plot legend). Plot from [1].

Dust clump emission

Once obtained the particle distribution, we use a canonical disc model to convert the dimensionless simulations to physical systems; by varying the gas density we obtain for each simulation 10 different physical systems characterised by different grain sizes; this is particularly useful as the mm opacity varies significantly with the grain size. We compute the grain opacity for the obtained grain sets (using the code by Birnstiel [5]) and apply a radiative transfer model to find the emitted flux, from which we then obtain ff (Eq. 1) and α (Eq. 2).

Figure 2 shows the distribution in the $ff - \alpha$ plane for one of our simulations. The blue squares represent the initial distribution of the 10 systems obtained from the conversion of the dimensionless simulation to physical units; the magenta diamonds show the systems' distribution after particle clumping; the black arrows link together the initial and final condition for the same system.

Figure 2: Distribution in the $ff - \alpha$ plane from [1]. The blue squares and the magenta diamonds show the distribution before and particle clumping, respectively. The black arrows link the initial condition of each system to its final condition.

Since the clumps are overdense, they are optically thicker than the initial particles' uniform distribution; as a consequence, when a particle goes in the clump, its emission is partially hidden. This explains why in all the systems we notice a decline in the optically thick fraction: some of the emission from grains in the uniform initial conditions is now hidden in optically thicker areas, causing a reduction of the overall flux declines and thus of the optically thick fraction. The spectral index, instead, can either increase or decrease, depending on the opacity index β (describing the opacity variation with the frequency) of clumping (big) particles. Recalling the relation between the spectral index and the opacity index (being B_ν the Planck function)

$$\alpha \sim \frac{\partial \log B_\nu}{\partial \log \nu} + \beta, \quad (3)$$

we notice that an increase (reduction) in β will produce an increase (reduction) in α . Since the contribution given by the smallest particles is always the same, because they remain in the uniform background, we deduce that the increase/decrease in α must be related to the value of β of the big (clumping) particles, whose emission is down-weighted after clump formation: if β of clumping particles is high (low) then α decreases (increases).

Results

We finally compare the simulations' and data distribution in the $ff - \alpha$ plane through the plot in Figure 3. The left panels refer to the group of simulations characterised by maximum Stokes number $\tau_{\max} = 0.1$, the right pan-

els refer to simulations with $\tau_{\max} = 1$; the upper panels show the distributions before particle clumping, the lower panels show the distribution after particle clumping. The different colours in the plot refers to different simulations (see the corresponding parameters in the plot legend), while the green stars show the data distribution. By comparing the upper and lower panels, we notice that the clump formation via streaming instability drives the simulations to the area of the plot occupied by the data.

Since the simulations refer to a local portion of the disc, whereas the data are based on measurements of flux emitted by the whole disc, we also define an integrated disc model (by mapping our simulations' results to different radii of the disc). We find that, provided that streaming instability takes place in a region of the disc which dominate the flux, also in the integrated disc model the action of streaming instability drives the simulations to the area of the $ff - \alpha$ plane occupied by the data.

We therefore conclude that the formation of dust clumps via streaming instability is consistent with the observations in the Lupus star forming region.

Figure 3: Distribution in the $ff - \alpha$ plane for all the simulations (see parameters in the legend) before (upper panels) and after (lower panels) clump formation. The data distribution is shown through the green stars. Plot from [1].

References

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Short CV

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